

ANALYSIS OF RAINFALL PATTERN FOR BHUJ TALUKA OF KUTCH DISTRICT – GUJARAT STATE

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ABSTRACT

The rainfall in Kutch District is very scanty and irregular and the district has very few rainy days. The average annual rainfall in the district is between 300 mm to 400 mm. The number of rainy days varies between 10 days to 17 days.

Bhuj is the capital of Kutch district. The Bhuj taluka is located in the central mainland of Kutch district. The region mostly consists of sandy clay soil. It has a geographical area of 458123 hectares. The average annual rainfall for Bhuj is 335 mm as against 356mm average annual rainfall of Kutch district.

Through this paper it is attempted to study the Rainfall Pattern for Bhuj taluka and compare it with that of Kutch district. For this purpose, annual rainfall data for a period of 130 years from 1878 to 2007 is studied and the probabilities of occurrence and dry and wet spells for the region have been determined.

ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Kutch is an ancient land possessed of great antiquity, which takes its name from its geographical characteristics and topographical features resembling a tortoise. This crescent shaped region forms part of the northwest Gujarat.

The district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. It is bounded on the north and north-west by Sindh (Pakistan), on the north-east by Rajasthan, on the east by the districts of Banaskantha and Mehsana, on the south-east by Surendranagar district, on the south by the Gulf of Kutch and the Rajkot district and on the south-west and west by the Arabian Sea. The district is roughly divided into four parts i.e Kutch mainland, Wagad region, Island belt comprising of four islands in the desert region and the Rann portion. Rapar taluka is a part of the Wagad region of Kutch.

The Bhuj taluka is located on the 23o 18" north latitude and 69o 42" east longitude. It lies on the central mainland region of the Kutch district. It includes a town of the same name (Bhuj) and 159 villages in the block. The town of Bhuj is situated towards the south east of the centre of Kutch, on relatively fertile land around hillocks. According to the 2001-Census, the total population of the district was 1,526,321 inhabitants. The total population of Bhuj city is estimated to be 344,783 or 39.54% of the total population of the district.

Figure 1 Location map for Kutch District and Bhuj taluka

Rainfall

The normal rainfall for Kutch district ranges between 300 to 400 mm. The district receives an average annual rainfall of 356 mm (for study period of 1878 to 2007), which is erratic and depends on the strength of the summer monsoon. It ranges from 335 mm at Bhuj to 452 mm at Naliya. It varies from 408 mm at Mandvi on the southern coast to 250 mm at Lakhpat on the northwest coast. The variation in the annual rainfall from the year to year is very large. The monsoon rains usually set in by the third week of June in the coastal belt and withdraws by the end of September. The maximum rainfall takes place during the month of July and very less rain occurs during the month of August and September. Most of annual rainfall in the district is received during the southwest monsoon season, July being the rainiest month. Rainfall of about 178 to 468 mm in a single day has also been recorded at many stations.

The average annual rainfall for Bhuj taluka is 335 mm. Table 1 shows the annual rainfall for Bhuj taluka as well as Kutch district for the period 1878 to 2007. It includes the analysis using moving mean method. Three year and five year moving mean values have been calculated for Bhuj taluka as well as Kutch district. During period 1878 to 2007 the highest annual rainfall amounting to 996 mm for Kutch district occurred in the year 1959 and 1269 mm for Bhuj taluka in the same year. Figure 2 shows the bar graphs and 3 year and 5 year moving mean graphs for Bhuj taluka as well as Kutch district.

Figure 2 Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall of Bhuj Taluka & Kutch District

Table 1 Comparison of Average Annual Rainfall for Bhuj Taluka and Kutch District
(Values in mm)

Year	Rainfall for Bhuj Taluka	Rainfall for Kutch District	3 year moving mean for Bhuj	3 year moving mean for Kutch	5 year moving mean for Bhuj	5 year moving mean for Kutch
1878	903	791				
1879	263	254	465	460		
1880	229	336	316	421	446	487
1881	455	673	354	464	347	420
1882	379	382	414	503	424	533
1883	408	455	478	552	450	518
1884	648	818	472	512	417	475
1885	359	262	433	512	400	471
1886	290	456	315	360	378	449
1887	295	362	294	388	329	349
1888	295	346	332	342	313	342
1889	407	317	327	297	285	302
1890	278	228	278	267	282	330
1891	150	255	235	329	284	334
1892	279	504	245	374	343	440
1893	307	364	429	572	349	442
1894	702	847	439	485	429	496
1895	308	243	520	538	441	503
1896	552	523	398	435	448	493
1897	335	539	410	458	312	328
1898	344	312	234	291	338	352
1899	22	24	268	232	247	270
1900	437	362	185	166	223	216
1901	95	114	249	248	249	232
1902	215	269	262	259	269	247
1903	475	394	271	253	214	212
1904	123	95	254	227	279	288
1905	163	190	234	259	312	326
1906	417	492	320	379	279	327
1907	381	456	370	450	349	404
1908	313	403	388	446	438	454
1909	470	481	465	441	367	371
1910	611	439	380	332	385	388
1911	59	76	380	352	338	444
1912	469	541	203	433	298	422
1913	82	683	273	531	216	367
1914	269	369	184	406	282	431
1915	200	165	287	310	346	461
1916	392	396	460	418	344	344
1917	787	694	416	396	351	339
1918	70	97	388	377	362	365
1919	307	341	210	245	294	377

1920	252	296	204	364	189	287
1921	52	455	190	332	204	290
1922	265	245	154	271	181	262
1923	144	114	200	186	152	235
1924	192	199	148	159	355	318
1925	108	164	455	410	399	366
1926	1065	868	553	505	427	389
1927	484	484	611	527	465	417
1928	285	230	383	350	491	447
1929	380	337	301	294	295	306
1930	239	316	236	273	236	290
1931	88	165	172	294	266	343
1932	189	402	236	354	250	350
1933	433	496	309	422	256	361
1934	304	369	335	413	274	391
1935	267	373	250	352	289	383
1936	178	315	237	350	251	335
1937	266	363	227	311	236	278
1938	238	254	244	234	230	251
1939	229	85	235	192	263	253
1940	238	235	271	216	260	222
1941	345	326	278	256	247	221
1942	251	208	256	261	301	328
1943	173	248	307	359	347	363
1944	499	620	379	427	334	349
1945	467	414	416	429	329	381
1946	282	254	324	345	316	352
1947	223	368	205	241	318	317
1948	109	103	281	306	367	313
1949	512	448	443	314	342	306
1950	710	392	459	354	364	308
1951	154	221	400	330	442	396
1952	336	377	330	380	439	384
1953	499	542	443	437	334	360
1954	496	392	394	400	410	399
1955	187	267	405	359	383	368
1956	531	419	307	303	336	344
1957	201	222	333	354	491	465
1958	265	421	579	546	486	439
1959	1269	996	567	518	550	499
1960	165	138	762	617	561	504
1961	851	718	423	368	550	442
1962	254	248	439	359	367	288
1963	211	110	273	194	402	318
1964	355	225	301	208	250	222
1965	338	290	262	251	343	327
1966	93	236	382	434	313	321
1967	716	775	291	364	257	290

1968	65	79	285	308	306	363
1969	73	69	241	268	338	371
1970	584	657	303	334	214	227
1971	252	276	310	329	241	238
1972	94	53	183	155	255	235
1973	204	137	147	81	230	174
1974	142	53	269	181	253	172
1975	460	353	323	223	290	223
1976	366	263	368	309	314	263
1977	279	310	323	303	453	411
1978	324	337	481	479	453	417
1979	839	790	539	505	452	449
1980	455	386	552	532	430	423
1981	363	419	330	329	413	432
1982	172	183	257	328	318	334
1983	236	381	258	288	252	299
1984	366	300	242	298	201	250
1985	123	212	198	229	167	218
1986	106	176	78	137	252	257
1987	5	22	256	258	291	280
1988	658	574	409	337	323	286
1989	563	414	501	411	317	270
1990	281	245	308	251	418	394
1991	80	93	290	328	302	302
1992	508	645	222	283	350	413
1993	79	111	462	576	328	411
1994	800	973	350	440	329	425
1995	172	236	353	457	291	411
1996	87	161	192	323	358	470
1997	317	573	273	380	262	329
1998	416	405	350	416	271	330
1999	318	269	318	305	303	372
2000	219	241	260	294	255	283
2001	243	372	180	247	314	348
2002	78	129	344	410	280	330
2003	712	728	313	346	274	341
2004	148	179	349	400	344	380
2005	188	294	311	347	465	463
2006	596	567	488	470	322	318
2007	680	548	425	372		

Source for annual rainfall data : Meteriological Department, Gandhinagar

Probability Analysis

Based on the above data, the probability of occurrence of different magnitudes of rainfall have been found out for Bhuj Taluka as well as Kutch district. The probability for rainfall occurring between 251 to 300 mm for Bhuj taluka is maximum while probability of the rainfall deviating from the average annual value by very high range i.e. below 50 mm or above 800 mm is very less. The probability of rainfall occurring between 350 to 400 mm for

Kutch district is maximum while the probability of rainfall deviating by more than 70 percent is very less.

Table 2 Probability of Occurrence of Rainfall For Kutch District

Rainfall in mm	Number of events	Probability of occurrence	% probability
0-50	2	0.0154	1.54
51-100	9	0.0692	6.92
101-150	8	0.0615	6.15
151-200	9	0.0692	6.92
201-251	16	0.1231	12.31
251-300	14	0.1077	10.77
301-350	11	0.0846	8.46
351-400	18	0.1385	13.85
401-450	10	0.0769	7.69
451-500	8	0.0615	6.15
501-550	6	0.0462	4.62
551-600	3	0.0231	2.31
601-650	2	0.0154	1.54
651-700	4	0.0308	3.08
701-750	2	0.0154	1.54
751-800	3	0.0231	2.31
801-850	2	0.0154	1.54
851-900	1	0.0077	0.77
901-950	0	0.0000	0.00
951-1000	2	0.0154	1.54

Table 3 Probability of Occurrence of Rainfall For Bhuj Taluka

Rainfall in mm	Number of events	Probability of occurrence	% probability
0-50	2	0.0154	1.54
51-100	14	0.1077	10.77
101-150	9	0.0692	6.92
151-200	12	0.0923	9.23
201-251	12	0.0923	9.23
251-300	20	0.1538	15.38
301-350	14	0.1077	10.77
351-400	8	0.0615	6.15
401-450	6	0.0462	4.62
451-500	11	0.0846	8.46
501-550	3	0.0231	2.31
551-600	4	0.0308	3.08
601-650	2	0.0154	1.54
651-700	2	0.0154	1.54
701-750	4	0.0308	3.08
751-800	2	0.0154	1.54
801-850	1	0.0077	0.77
851-900	1	0.0077	0.77
901-950	1	0.0077	0.77
951-1000	0	0.0000	0.00
1001-1050	0	0.0000	0.00
1051-1100	0	0.0000	0.00
1101-1150	0	0.0000	0.00
1151-1200	1	0.0077	0.77
1201-1250	0	0.0000	0.00
1251-1300	1	0.0077	0.77

Figure 3 Probability of Occurrence of Rainfall For Bhuj Taluka and Kutch District

Surplus and Deficit Year Analysis

The annual rainfall during the study period has been classified as drought, deficit, normal, above average and surplus according to the following criteria.

Table 4 Criteria for analysis of Rainfall

Sr. No.	Description	Rainfall in mm
1	Drought years	<150
2	Rainfall deficit years	151-300
3	Normal Rainfall years	300-400
4	Above average rainfall years	400-500
5	Surplus rainfall years	> 500

Table 5 Rainfall analysis for Kutch District

Drought years	Rainfall deficit years	Normal Rainfall years	Above average rainfall years	Surplus rainfall years
1891, 1899, 1901, 1904, 1911, 1913, 1918, 1921, 1923, 1925, 1931, 1948, 1966, 1968, 1969, 1972, 1974, 1985, 1986, 1987, 1991, 1993, 1996, 2002, 2004	1879, 1880, 1886, 1887, 1888, 1890, 1892, 1902, 1905, 1914, 1915, 1920, 1922, 1924, 1928, 1930, 1932, 1935, 1936, 1937, 1938, 1939, 1940, 1942, 1943, 1946, 1947, 1951, 1955, 1957, 1958, 1960, 1962, 1963, 1971, 1973, 1977, 1982, 1983, 1990, 1995, 2000, 2001, 2005	1882, 1885, 1893, 1895, 1897, 1898, 1907, 1908, 1916, 1919, 1929, 1934, 1941, 1952, 1964, 1965, 1976, 1978, 1980, 1981, 1984, 1997, 1999	1881, 1883, 1889, 1900, 1903, 1906, 1909, 1912, 1927, 1933, 1944, 1945, 1953, 1954, 1975, 1998	1878, 1884, 1894, 1896, 1910, 1917, 1926, 1949, 1950, 1956, 1959, 1961, 1967, 1970, 1979, 1988, 1989, 1992, 1994, 2003, 2006, 2007
Total 19 years	Total 39 years	Total 29 years	Total 18 years	Total 25 years

Table 6 Rainfall analysis for Bhuj Taluka

Drought years	Rainfall deficit years	Normal Rainfall years	Above average rainfall years	Surplus rainfall years
1899, 1901, 1904, 1911, 1918, 1923, 1939, 1948, 1960, 1963, 1968, 1969, 1972, 1973, 1974, 1987, 1991, 1993, 2002	1879, 1885, 1890, 1891, 1895, 1902, 1905, 1915, 1920, 1922, 1924, 1925, 1928, 1931, 1938, 1940, 1942, 1943, 1946, 1951, 1955, 1957, 1962, 1964, 1965, 1966, 1971, 1976, 1982, 1984, 1985, 1986, 1990, 1995, 1996, 1999, 2000, 2004, 2005	1880, 1882, 1887, 1888, 1889, 1893, 1898, 1900, 1903, 1914, 1916, 1919, 1929, 1930, 1934, 1935, 1936, 1937, 1941, 1947, 1950, 1952, 1954, 1975, 1977, 1978, 1980, 1983, 2001	1883, 1886, 1906, 1907, 1908, 1909, 1910, 1921, 1927, 1932, 1933, 1945, 1949, 1956, 1958, 1981, 1989, 1998	1878, 1881, 1884, 1892, 1894, 1896, 1897, 1912, 1913, 1917, 1926, 1944, 1953, 1959, 1961, 1967, 1970, 1979, 1988, 1992, 1994, 1997, 2003, 2006, 2007
Total 25 years	Total 44 years	Total 23 years	Total 16 years	Total 22 years

Total 19 years	Total 39 years	Total 29 years	Total 18 years	Total 25 years
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Conclusions

For the study period of 1878 to 2007, the Bhuj taluka experienced drought for a period of 25 years as compared to 19 years for Kutch district. There were 44 rainfall deficit years for Bhuj taluka as compared to 39 years for Kutch district. There was normal rainfall for 23 years for Bhuj taluka as compared to 29 years for Kutch district. There was rainfall above average annual value for a total of 16 years in Bhuj taluka as compared to 18 years in Kutch district. There was surplus rainfall for 22 years in Bhuj taluka as compared to 25 years for Kutch district.

It can be concluded that Bhuj taluka has experienced more number of years as drought, rainfall deficit years as compared to Kutch district while it has experienced less number of years for normal rainfall, above average and surplus rainfall.

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